

Arboreality in the typhlopid *Madatyphlops ocellaris* from north-eastern Madagascar, with a review of climbing behaviour in scolecophidian snakes

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Abstract

Scolecophidians (blind or thread snakes) are a diverse taxon typically characterized as strictly fossorial snakes that are highly adapted to subterranean lifestyle. However, reports of climbing behaviour in various species underline the gaps in our knowledge regarding the behaviour of these secretive animals. Here, we present the first record of arboreality in the Madagascar-endemic typhlopid *Madatyphlops ocellaris* (Parker, 1927) based on observations of three individuals, constituting the second published report of climbing behaviour in Malagasy blind snakes. We furthermore provide the first reliably identified photographs of this species in life, review the distribution of this species, and discuss possible functions of the climbing behaviour such as mate-attraction.

Scolecophidians are often employed as model organisms for investigating fossoriality (Measey, 2006; Herrel et al., 2021; Tiatragul et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2025) and show a high degree of physiological and anatomical adaptation to this lifestyle (Da Silva et al., 2018; Chretien et al., 2019). Whilst their systematic origin and morphology are decrypted with increasing effort (Miralles et al., 2018), their behaviour remains vastly understudied (Graboski et al., 2023). This is highlighted by numerous reports of climbing behaviour in 27 species within three families across the scolecophidean tree of life (Table 1), without scientific consensus regarding its function (Ugalde et al., 2025).

Madatyphlops ocellaris is one of 12 endemic species of scolecophidian snakes known from Madagascar. One of these species (*Xenotyphlops grandidieri*) belongs to the monotypic family Xenotyphlopidae (Wegener et al., 2013), whereas the other 11 species belong to the genus *Madatyphlops* in the family Typhlopidae (Renoult and Raselimanana, 2009; Wallach and Glaw, 2009). *Madatyphlops ocellaris* is very poorly known and has been classified as Data Deficient by the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Vences and Raselimanana, 2011). Apart from its type locality "Antongil forest, Maroantsetra, N. E. Madagascar" (Parker 1927), abbreviated to Maroantsetra by Guibé (1958), the species has been recorded from

Manantantely and the Vohimena Mountains (Nussbaum et al., 1999), Marojejy National Park, 640–700 m a.s.l. (Raselimanana et al., 2000) and the Fianarantsoa region, based on specimen FMNH 261369 (Wallach and Glaw, 2009; Fig. 1D). In addition, a record from Vohimana (-18.92122, 48.51604, accuracy 146 m) on iNaturalist (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/19120373>) strongly resembles and most likely also belongs to *M. ocellaris*.

Here, we present the first record of arboreality in the Madagascar-endemic typhlopidae *Madatyphlops ocellaris* (Parker, 1927), constituting the second published report in Malagasy blind snakes (Glaw and Vences, 1994). Between 1st and 3rd November 2024, three climbing specimens (FGZC 7058–7059, FGZC 7090) and one individual on the ground (FGZC 7077) were spotted in the rainforest corridor connecting the Makira National Park and the Masoala National Park (Fig. 1A–C; Suppl. File 1), close to the Camp Ambatolaidama (15°17'42"S, 50°0'29"E, about 400 m a.s.l.; Fig. 1A). The specimens were collected, euthanized, and subsequently stored at the Bavarian State Collection of Zoology (ZSM), Munich, Germany, and the University of Antananarivo (UADBA), Madagascar. FGZC refers to field numbers of F. Glaw.

Specimens were found in-situ as follows:

- (1) UADBA-FGZC 7058: found near camp Ambatolaidama climbing in a network of vines at about 1 m above ground on 1st November 2024 at around 7:20 pm (Fig. 1C); it was observed climbing belly-up and with active tongue-flicking.
- (2) ZSM-FGZC 7059: found near camp Ambatolaidama climbing a thin, vertical sapling stem alongside a path at about 60 cm above ground on 2nd November 2024 at around 10:00 pm (Fig. 1D; Suppl. File 1); it was found after (not during) light rainfall. After being spotted, it slowly descended downwards, head-first. This unsexed specimen had a snout-vent length of 318 mm, tail length 10.0 mm, head width 4.6 mm, head length 7.5 mm, 20 scale rows around midbody, 585 total middorsals, 22 subcaudals, and apical spine present.
- (3) UADBA-FGZC 7090: spotted near camp Ambatolaidama curled up on a scandent bamboo on a tree, approximately 2 m above ground on 3rd November 2024 at around 7:00 pm (Fig. 1A).

A fourth specimen (ZSM-FGZC 7077) was found crawling above the ground on the forest floor of a path near camp Ambatolaidama on 3rd November 2024 at around 08:30 pm. Heavy rainfall followed the next day. This unsexed specimen had a snout-vent length of 317 mm, tail length 9.8 mm, head width 4.5 mm, head length 8.1 mm, 20 scale rows around midbody, 565 total middorsals, 19 subcaudals, and apical spine present (Fig. 1E).

All four specimens were very similar to each other, having a uniformly pinkish-brown coloration in life (Fig. 1A–C), comparatively large black eyes with distinctly visible pupils covered by head scales, and a pointed rostral scale (Fig. 1E). These traits, together with the meristic values reported above for the two specimens deposited in the ZSM, unambiguously identify this snake species as *M. ocellaris* according to the identification key of Wallach and Glaw (2009). Whilst specimens deposited at the ZSM were sufficiently studied, UADBA specimens were identified as *M. ocellaris* in the field only.

Arboreality has been reported in another *Madatyphlops* species before, i.e., *M. arenarius* (Grandidier, 1872), which was found near St. Augustin, south-western Madagascar (Fig. 1A), climbing up on the bark of a larger tree at about 1.5 m height (Glaw and Vences, 1994). Furthermore, an observation uploaded to iNaturalist by Nicolas Cliquennois on 16th July 2022

shows a not further identifiable *Madatyphlops* sp. climbing branches of a tree in Forêt d'Ambodiriana (16°40'19.6"S, 49°42'00.8"E, accuracy 433 m) on 26th December 2007 (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/126499703>, accessed on 19th October 2025). Although we cannot identify the species from the photo, it is quite possible that this observation also refers to *M. ocellaris*.

The reason for this climbing behaviour in scolecophidians is poorly understood (Ugalde et al., 2025). It is frequently described as being part of foraging behaviour, e.g., they follow chemical cues of their prey—ants or termites (Swanson, 1981; Shine and Webb, 1990; Das and Wallach, 1998; Landestoy T., 2023). However, we did not spot any termite or ant tracks in immediate vicinity to the climbing specimens—though tongue-flicking was observed in all of our climbing *Madatyphlops ocellaris* specimens. Gaulke (1995) proposed a part-time arboreality in *Ramphotyphlops suluensis* (Taylor, 1918) with active foraging in the trees at nighttime, while using epiphytes only as daytime-retreats. Thus, scolecophidians may use climbing behaviour to exploit new foraging niches without the need for chemical signals from potential prey (Vanzolini, 1970; Bazzano, 2007). Gehlbach and Baldrige (1987) reported *Rena dulcis* (Baird and Girard, 1853) in eastern screech owl (*Megascops asio*) nests in Texas, USA, living putatively in commensalism with them after being actively collected by the birds. They argue that the snakes feed on insects emerging from feces, pellets, and uneaten prey, improving nest hygiene and, hence, owl nestling fitness. A similar case was reported by Göçer et al. (2025) who located *Xerotyphlops vermicularis* in nests of Eurasian scops owls (*Otus scops*) in Türkiye, associated with an increased owl hatchling success rate.

In some cases, seasonal flooding may induce arboreality as indicated by Vanzolini (1970) for leptotyphlopids of the periodically flooded Amazonian forests. We do not consider this explanation to be likely for the climbing *Madatyphlops ocellaris* which were spotted in the dry season, although it has to be taken into account that the observations were made shortly before heavy rainfall set in.

An alternative explanation may link scolecophidian climbing behaviour to inter- or intraspecific communication, such as mate-attraction utilizing or following pheromone trails (Gaulke, 1995; Das and Wallach, 1998). Watkins et al. (1969) found discharged cloacal sac contents of *Rena dulcis* to repel ants and colubrid snakes, but attract conspecifics of both sexes. It is, therefore, plausible for them to reach higher places to secrete pheromones more effectively or to follow trails left by conspecifics. Hence, we suspect this to be the most likely scenario.

Reports of arboreality in various scolecophidian species have laid the groundwork for subsequent large-scale studies, but no systematic investigation of arboreal or climbing behaviour in this group exists so far. The origin and underlying causes of this peculiar behaviour therefore remain speculative.

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Conflicts of Interest

Commented [FJ1]: Linah or James, could you please add Niaina's last name? Thanks!

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Data availability

A supplementary video file (Suppl. File 1) is available on both Zenodo and YouTube under the following links: [LINKS AFTER ACCEPTANCE OF THE MANUSCRIPT]

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Appendix

Supplementary File 1: Short video showing the in situ climbing behaviour of a *Madatyphlops ocellaris* specimens (FGZC 7059) found near camp Ambatolaidama climbing a thin, vertical sapling stem alongside a path on 2nd November 2024 at around 10:00 pm.

Tables

Table 1: Summary of literature reports (including one record from iNaturalist) of climbing behaviour or arboreality in scolecophidian snakes.

FAMILY	SPECIES	LOCATION	SOURCE
GERRHOPILIDAE	<i>Gerrhopilus addisoni</i> Kraus, 2017	Panaete Island, Papua New Guinea	Kraus (2017)
	<i>Gerrhopilus inornatus</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	Papua New Guinea	Kraus (2017)
	<i>Gerrhopilus persephone</i> Kraus, 2017	Normanby Island, Papua New Guinea	Kraus (2017)
LEPTOTYPHLOPIDAE	<i>Epictia albifrons</i> (Wagler, 1824)	Kartabo, Guyana; Itapiranga, Brazil	Beebe (1946); Vanzolini (1970)
	<i>Epictia tenella</i> (Klauber, 1939)	Trinidad, Republic of Trinidad and Tobago; Jari riverbanks, Brazil	Das and Wallach (1998); Murphy et al. (2016); Fraga and Carvalho (2022); Mole (1924), unclear: “under the bark of trees”
	<i>Epictia tessellata</i> (Tschudi, 1845)	Lima, Peru	Schmidt and Walker, Jr. (1943), unclear: “collected in the wall of an old adobe house”
	<i>Mitophis pyrites</i> (Thomas, 1965)	Hispaniola, Dominican Republic	Landestoy T. (2023)
	<i>Myriopholis macrorhyncha</i> (Jan, 1860)	Pakistan	Minton, Jr. (1966)
	<i>Rena dulcis</i> Baird and Girard, 1853	Waco, Texas, USA; McLennan County, Texas, USA	Vanzolini (1970); Gehlbach and Baldrige (1987)
TYPHLOPIDAE	<i>Trilepida macrolepis</i> (Peters, 1858)	Mariquita, Colombia	Dunn (1944)
	<i>Trilepida salgueiroi</i> (Amaral, 1955)	Niterói, Brazil	Ugalde et al. (2025)
	<i>Amerotyphlops brongersmianus</i> (Vanzolini, 1976)	São João do Jabuti, Brazil	Lozorio et al. (2025)
	<i>Anilius australis</i> Gray, 1845	Australia	Chapman and Dell (1975)
	<i>Anilius nigrescens</i> Gray, 1845	Australia	Shine and Webb (1990)
	<i>Antillytyphlops catapontus</i> (Thomas, 1966)	Puerto Rico	Lazell (2006)
	<i>Antillytyphlops richardii</i> (Duméril and Bibron, 1844)	Puerto Rico	Tolson and Campbell (1989)
	<i>Indotyphlops braminus</i> (Daudin, 1803)	Southern India; Darwin, Australia; Car Nicobar, India; Hawaii, USA	Annandale (1906); Swanson (1981); Das and Wallach (1998); Bazzano (2007)
	<i>Madatyphlops arenarius</i> (Grandidier, 1872)	Near St. Augustin, Madagascar	Glaw and Vences (1994)
	<i>Madatyphlops ocularis</i> (Parker, 1927)	Ambatolaidama, Madagascar	Reported for the first time here
	<i>Madatyphlops</i> sp.	Forêt d'Ambodiriana, Madagascar	iNaturalist (https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/126499703)
	<i>Ramphotyphlops angusticeps</i> (Peters, 1878)	Guadalcanal, Solomon Islands	McCoy (1980); Das and Wallach (1998)
	<i>Ramphotyphlops cumingii</i> (Gray, 1845)	Bunawan, Mindanao, Philippines	Taylor (1919)
	<i>Ramphotyphlops depressus</i> Peters, 1880	Manus Island, Papua New Guinea	Das and Wallach (1998); Kraus (2017)
	<i>Ramphotyphlops olivaceus</i> (Gray, 1845)	Seram, Maluku, Eastern Indonesia	Edgar and Lilley (1993), specified in Das and Wallach (1998)
<i>Ramphotyphlops suluensis</i> (Taylor, 1918)	Sibutu island, Philippines	Gaulke (1995)	
<i>Typhlops lumbricalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	New Providence, Bahamas	Schwartz and Henderson (1991)	
<i>Typhlops sulcatus</i> Cope, 1868	Hispaniola, Dominican Republic	Landestoy T. (2023)	
<i>Xerotyphlops vermicularis</i> (Merrem, 1820)	Türkiye	Göçer et al. (2025)	

Figures

Figure 1: Arboreality in and distribution of *Madatyphlops ocularis*. (A–C) Specimens photographed in situ climbing on tree stems, branches, and vines, as described in the text: (A) FGZC 7090, (B) FGZC 7059, (C) FGZC 7058; (D) Distribution of *M. ocularis* in Madagascar; (E) Photographs of the preserved specimen FGZC 7077 (from left to right): head dorsal, head lateral (right side), head ventral, tail lateral with apical spine (right side).